

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY OF COPPER ALIZARIN SULPHONATE COMPLEX

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Alizarin Red S forms coloured complexes with various metals and has been employed for the colorimetric determination of aluminium, uranium and thorium. The colour reactions, however, are not specific and are subject to interference by various metallic ions.

The formation of copper alizarin sulphonate has been investigated by the spectrophotometric method and Beer's law has been observed not to obey with different mixtures having varying amounts of copper and a large excess of the dye. The dye can be recommended as a colorimetric reagent for the determination of copper.

By Job's method of continuous variation the complex appears to possess the composition having the reactants in the ratio of 1:1. The value of the formation constant at 28° has been calculated to be $3.5 \pm 0.4 \times 10^5$ and free energy of formation to be -7.63 Kcals.

The structure of copper alizarin sulphonate has been discussed and it has been suggested that the two phenolic hydrogens are replaced by bivalent copper to form the complex

Sodium alizarin sulphonate (Alizarin Red S) is known to produce characteristic colour reactions with many inorganic ions. This property has been utilised in the colorimetric determination of metal ions in dilute solutions (Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1950, p. 123). Alizarin Red S has also been successfully employed for the colorimetric determination of aluminium (Poole, "B.D.H. Book of Organic Reagents", 1949, p. 4) and the interference of various ions has been discussed by Parker and Goddard (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 4, 517). Raghava Rao and co-workers investigated the complex formation between Alizarin Red S and uranium and thorium (*ibid.*, 1955, 13, 79, 142) and suggested the dye as a suitable reagent for the estimation of these metals. Ware (U.S. Atomic Energy Comm. Rep., MDDC, 1945, p. 1432), however, does not recommend the dye for the determination of uranyl ion. In a recent publication Mukherji and Dey (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A,) have shown that Alizarin Red S produces an orange colour with dilute solutions of copper sulphate, having a maximum absorption at $500 \text{ m}\mu$; they discussed the effect of p_{H} changes on the colour of the dye and have sought to explain the colour changes on the basis of Kuhn's formula (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 840; 1949, 17, 1108) while considering the different ionising structures in the presence of varying concentrations of hydrogen ions. They have also investigated the composition, stability and free energy of formation of lead alizarin sulphonate complex by the spectrophotometric method (*loc. cit.*).

In the present communication the spectrophotometric study of the system CuSO_4 -Alizarin Red S, using various concentrations of the reactants, has been made. The composition and structure of the complex formed have been discussed and the formation constant and the free energy of formation of the complex calculated at 28°.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Standard solutions of CuSO_4 (B.D.H. Anala R) and Alizarin Red S (B.D.H. Indicator) were prepared using double distilled water. For the measurement of optical density Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer was employed and the measurements conducted in an air-conditioned room at 28° . The mixtures were kept at least for 15 minutes after mixing to attain equilibrium. For every measurement 1 cm thickness of the solutions was used in glass cells supplied along with the instrument.

Validity of Beer's Law.—In a set of experiments to a fixed quantity of the dye were added varying quantities of CuSO_4 solution, keeping in view that the amount of the dye always remained in large excess as compared to that of CuSO_4 . The total volume was made constant by the addition of water and the optical densities of the different mixtures measured at a wave-length of $500 \text{ m}\mu$. The observations were repeated at different concentrations of the dye and CuSO_4 and it was concluded that Beer's law was not rigidly obeyed.

Nature of Complexes formed.—In another set of experiments, mixtures containing varying proportions of copper: Alizarin Red S (i.e. 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 etc.) were prepared and the optical densities of the solutions at different wave-lengths in each case measured. In all the cases the maximum absorption occurred at a spectral region of $500 \text{ m}\mu$, thus indicating the formation of only one complex with the reagent (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437).

Composition of the Complex.—Job's method of continuous variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1928, 180, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) was adopted. The total volume in each case was kept 50 c.c. Some of the typical results are recorded in Tables I and II. It may be mentioned that at the dilution and wave-length used ($500 \text{ m}\mu$) copper sulphate solution had no absorption.

TABLE I

Volume of CuSO_4		$\text{CuSO}_4 (c) = 5M \times 10^{-4}$ Dye $(c) = 5M \times 10^{-4}$ p_H of the mixtures = 3.7 to 4.1. $p = c'/c = 1$.		$\text{CuSO}_4 (c) = 3.33M \times 10^{-4}$ Dye $(c) = 3.33M \times 10^{-4}$ p_H of the mixtures = 3.9 to 4.3. $p = c'/c = 1$.		$\text{CuSO}_4 (c) = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ Dye $(c) = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ p_H of the mixtures = 4.0 to 4.4. $p = c'/c = 1$.	
Dye.		Optical density of the Mixture.	Optical density of the Dye.	Optical density of the Mixture	Optical density of the Dye.	Optical density of the Mixture.	Optical density of the Dye.
0 c.c.	50 c.c.	0.190	0.190	0.150	0.150	0.170	0.170
5	45	0.310	0.180	0.230	0.140	0.180	0.190
10	40	0.400	0.160	0.300	0.130	0.250	0.180
15	35	0.470	0.140	0.330	0.100	0.280	0.090
20	30	0.500	0.125	0.370	0.080	0.310	0.060
25	25	0.520	0.110	0.380	0.070	0.320	0.070
30	20	0.490	0.100	0.370	0.070	0.300	0.060
35	15	0.450	0.070	0.330	0.050	0.260	0.050
40	10	0.360	0.060	0.260	0.035	0.210	0.040
45	5	0.220	0.050	0.140	0.020	0.120	0.030

The peaks of the curves occur at a ratio of 1:1.

TABLE II

		Conc. of CuSO_4 (c) = $5.0M \times 10^{-4}$. Conc. of the dye (c') = $3.33M \times 10^{-4}$. p_H of the mixtures = 3.7 to 4.2. $p = c'/c = 2/3$.			Conc. of CuSO_4 (c) = $3.33M \times 10^{-4}$. Conc. of the dye (c') = $5.00M \times 10^{-4}$. p_H of the mixtures = 3.9 to 4.2. $p = c'/c = 3/2$.		
CuSO ₄ .	Volume of Dye.	Optical density of the Mixture.		Diff.	Optical density of the Mixture.		Diff.
		(a)	(b)		(a)	(b)	
0 c.c.	50 c.c.	0.150	0.150	...	0.190	0.190	...
5	45	0.310	0.140	0.170	0.290	0.180	0.110
10	40	0.370	0.130	0.240	0.350	0.160	0.190
15	35	0.410	0.100	0.310	0.400	0.140	0.260
20	30	0.440	0.080	0.360	0.430	0.125	0.305
25	25	0.430	0.070	0.360	0.450	0.110	0.340
30	20	0.420	0.070	0.350	0.440	0.100	0.340
35	15	0.380	0.050	0.330	0.410	0.070	0.340
40	10	0.290	0.035	0.255	0.340	0.060	0.280
45	5	0.140	0.020	0.120	0.210	0.050	0.160

The peaks of the curves occur at a ratio of 1:1.

We conclude that only one complex forms at a ratio of 1:1 of the reactants. It may further be mentioned that it has been experimentally ascertained that no appreciable change in colour occurs in the dye for a small change in the p_H value which accompanies the addition of copper sulphate to Alizarin Red S.

DISCUSSION

For the determination of the composition of the coloured complex, Job's method of continuous variation (*loc. cit.*) has been employed using optical density as a guide of the complex formation. For a constant total concentration of the metallic ion and complexing agent, the concentration of the complex is greatest when metal and complexing agent are present in the system in the ratio in which they exist in the complex (cf. Martell and Calvin, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice-Hall, New York, 1953, p. 29). If the complex is the only coloured substance present in the system, the optical density of the solution is proportional to the concentration of the complex. Hence, a graph, showing the variation of optical density with composition of the system, would afford a curve with a maximum at the composition corresponding to the formula of the complex. In our case, however, the dye has an absorption in the same region as the complex, whereas cupric ions do not show any absorption at the wave-length and dilution employed. Job (*loc. cit.*) stated that the method was not applicable to systems

in which more than one compound was formed, while Vosburgh and Cooper (*loc. cit.*) were able to apply the method to a special case in which they determined the equilibria involving three chelate compounds.

FIG. 1

For the determination of the stability constants we have employed the data plotted in Fig. 1, where the observed optical density (not the difference in optical density) has been plotted against $[Cu^{2+}]/([Cu^{2+}]+[R])$. It may be assumed that in the descending portion of the curve, where Cu^{2+} ions are in excess, most of the dye is bound up in the complex and therefore the optical density of the free dye does not contribute substantially to the optical density of the system. Hence, the observed optical density is mainly due to the colour of the complex. We may therefore assume that in curves A, B and C at the points, where the optical densities are the same (say 0.2), the amounts of complex formed are identical.

For the system : $mA + nB = A_mB_n$

where ($m/n = 1$, or $m = n = 1$) the formation constant

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where x is the concentration of the complex, and a and b are the initial concentrations of CuSO_4 and Alizarin Red S respectively. Taking the two concentrations a_1 and a_2 and b_1 and b_2 of the reactants, giving the same optical density, that is, the same values of x_1 and x_2 , we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-x)} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-x)} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

or

$$x = \frac{a_1b_1 - a_2b_2}{(a_1 - b_1) - (a_2 - b_2)} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Knowing the value of x in equation (3), the value of K can be found out by substitution in equation (1).

We have calculated the values of the formation constant (at 0.2 of the optical density in the curves A, B and C of Fig. 1) and the average value comes out to be $3.5 \pm 0.4 \times 10^5$. The dissociation constant therefore works out to be 2.86×10^{-6} . The free energy in terms of the dissociation constant K_d is represented by $\Delta F = RT \log K_d$, where the terms have their usual significance. In this system the value of ΔF at a temperature of 28° works out to be -7630 calories.

It is customary to calculate the values of the formation constant by "swamping" the complexing agent with simple ions in order to obtain systems of constant ionic strength. It was not possible in our case, because the dye itself was susceptible to colour changes by the addition of neutral salts like KCl, NaCl etc. Moreover, the solutions employed by us were extremely dilute and were of the order of $10^{-4} M$.

Alizarin Red S is capable of existing in three ionisable forms depending upon the p_H of the medium. The alizarin molecule can be represented by the following three structures :

Since the ratio of the reactants for the formation of the complex is 1 : 1, the value of $[Cu^{2+}]/([Cu^{2+}] + [R])$ being 0.5 at the peaks of the curves, the structure of the complex is likely to be

similar to zirconyl and hafnium alizarinates, as investigated by Leibhafsky and Winslow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1130) and Larsen and Hirozawa (*J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1956, 3, 198).

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